

LIGHTNING STRIKE PROTECTION FOR COMPOSITE LAMINATES BY PITCH-BASED CARBON FIBER SKIN

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1. Introduction

In order to fulfill the growing demand for wind turbines needed to generate electricity efficiently, larger turbine blades have been researched earnestly [1]. Because larger blades are likely to bend easily, high modulus carbon fiber, especially pitch-based carbon fiber, seems suitable for turbine blade material [2].

Lightning strike is a primary threat for composite structures, such as wind turbine blades and aircraft structures, exposed under the sky. In order to prevent damage to composite structures by lightning strikes, various kinds of protections have been developed [3, 4]. For example, electrically conductive materials such as Aluminium and Copper meshes are used for lightning strike protection on composite aircraft structures [3]. In addition, several research on fracture behaviour caused by lightning strike on carbon fiber reinforced plastics (CFRP) were reported [5, 6]. Nevertheless, it has been difficult to protect composites completely from damages caused by lightning strikes.

Regarding to wind turbine blades, protection systems such as receptors and down conductors are standard techniques [7]. However, these systems are also likely to be damaged due to lightning strikes, and therefore, eventually do not protect the blades as

designed. In order to protect the blades long term, it would be expected that the blades themselves should have from damage by lightning strikes, it would be sufficient properties, including high electrical and thermal conductivity. Since pitch-based carbon fiber has such suitable properties [8, 9], we explored applying pitch-based carbon fiber skin to laminates in order to improve lightning strike resistance for wind turbine blades.

2. Experiment

Specimen panels were 150mm square and consisted of common core layer with different skin layers, as shown in Table 1. Typically, a core layer had 5 mm thickness and was made of unidirectional prepreg with standard Poly Acrylonitrile based carbon fiber (PAN-CF, TR 50S by Mitsubishi Rayon) and epoxy resins of 120°C except of specimen A, whose core layer was composed of unidirectional prepreg with PAN-CF (MR 50 by Mitsubishi Rayon) and epoxy resins of 180°C cure. The prepreg used as core layer of specimen A was laminated as 0° with the center layer, which had 90° direction. Skin layers had varied thickness and were made of +/-45° layup of unidirectional prepreg with different carbon fibers. Fibers used in skin panels were PAN-CF: TR 50S

Table 1 Laminate Conditions

Specimen	Core layer		Skin layer as a part				
	Carbon fiber	Thickness [mm]	Carbon fiber	Property as fiber		Direction	Thickness [mm]
				Thermal Conductivity	Electrical Resistivity		
				[W/mK]	[$\mu\Omega$ m]		
A	MR 50	5.2	K13C2U	620	1.9	+/- 45°	1.0
B	TR 50S	5.0	K63712	140	6.6	+/- 45°	1.0
C	TR 50S	5.0	TR 50S	30	15.5	+/- 45°	1.0
D	TR 50S	5.0	K63712	140	6.6	+/- 45°	0.5
E	TR 50S	5.0	TR 50S	30	15.5	+/- 45°	0.5
F	TR 50S	5.0	K13C2U	620	1.9	+/- 45°	0.6
G	TR 50S	5.0	K13916	200	5.1	+/- 45°	1.0
H	TR 50S	5.0	K13916	200	5.1	+/- 45°	0.5
I	TR 50S	5.0	K13916	200	5.1	+/- 45°	0.1
J	TR 50S	5.0	K63712	140	6.6	+/- 45°	0.2

and pitch-based carbon fiber: K13C2U, K63712 and K13916 produced by Mitsubishi Plastics. Each skin panel was laminated on both sides of the core layer. Laminate conditions are listed in Table 1. In order to simulate lightning strikes, Haefely Test AG's impulse current generator (ICG, Fig. 1) was used in this study. The testing conditions and setups were referred to in prior article [4, 10] and are listed in Table 2. A typical tested waveform (Testing condition IV) is shown in Fig. 2. Pictures before and after a lightning strike test are seen in Fig. 3 (Specimen E, testing condition IV). To investigate artificial lightning struck specimens, visual appearances were observed. In addition, non destructive inspection was performed using ultrasonic testing. Model of the ultrasonic testing (UT) system was SONDA 007CX, produced by Quality Material Inspection, Inc. The inspection was conducted with 400Hz and specimens were scanned by 2mm*2mm pitch. Cross sectional observations were conducted with a microscope (produced by Olympus) after specimen were cut (fig. 4).

Fig. 2 Typical tested wave form, condition number IV

(a) Overview

(b) Discharge probe

Fig.1 Impulse current generator (ICG)

a) Before a lightning strike test

b) After the test

Fig 3 Pictures of a Specimen E, test condition IV

Fig. 4 Cross sectional observations

Table 2 Testing condition

	ICG charging voltage	peak current [kA]	Electric current waveform wave peak/wave tail		Electrical charge [C]	Specific energy [kJ/ohm]
	(polarity) [kV]		T1 [μ s]	T2 [μ s]		
I	-22 (negative)	39 to 41	9 to 10	26	0.8	26 to 29
II	+45 (positive)	83 to 85	9 to 10	26	1.6	117 to 124
III	-65 (negative)	121 to 124	9 to 10	26	2.3	253 to 262
IV	+82 (positive)	151 to 157	9 to 10	26	3.0	396 to 422

3. Results and discussion

3.1 Effects of Test conditions

In this paper, results of lightning tests on specimen panels that have different skin panels are reported. In order to clearly distinguish protective abilities of different kinds of them, lightning strike tests on specimen A were conducted under four different conditions as shown in Table 2. From condition I to condition IV, stronger lightning strikes were imposed on specimens. Visual appearances of tested specimen panels were observed and their damaged areas were also inspected and calculated as an area of diamond by multiplying damaged lengths, described as arrows in Fig. 5 (Specimen B, Condition III). In this figure, the core layer was aligned with width direction. As for visual appearances of tested specimens, it was observed that the stronger the lightning strike testing conditions become, the larger damaged areas became (Fig. 6). Fig 6b-d depicted area of tested specimen near the area where the lightning struck lost fiber in skin panels. The damaged area appeared to be along the direction of carbon fiber in skin panels. Since carbon fiber unidirectional prepreg has anisotropic thermal and electrical conductivity, damages propelled along the direction that carbon fiber was aligned.

For further investigation of damage, caused by lightning strikes, UT was applied to tested specimens (Fig. 7). Visual images obtained from UT were adjusted as the normal parts of specimens showed gray color (though the color was green on display of the UT system, actually). According to attenuation of ultrasonic, color of obtained images turns darker color (though the color was red on display of the UT system, actually). Therefore, darker area on an image shows that the defaults existed in the area. In accordance with the strengthened testing conditions, UT results of specimens also showed larger damage area. Closer visual appearance of tested specimen A under condition IV and the UT result were shown in Fig. 8. By comparing these images in Fig. 8, area where delaminations occurred was described as darker color (red color on the color display). On the

other hand, areas where carbon fiber was lost showed gray color (green color on the color display) in Fig. 8b. Since the carbon fiber lost area did not have delaminations, no significant attenuation of ultrasonic would have been observed. Applying UT enables to distinguish delaminations and fiber lost clearly.

To investigate internal damage, cross sectional observations were conducted and damaged depth of each specimen was investigated (Fig. 9). While the specimen under condition I did not show any significant damage (Fig. 9a), specimens in the other conditions showed damages (Fig. 9b-d). Under condition II, III and IV, delamination was observed in these specimens. Particularly, in Fig. 9d, not only delamination, but also lost of carbon fiber in the center area of the specimen was appeared. Although skin panels were damaged in condition II, III, IV, no damage in core layer was observed.

Taking investigation results as shown in Fig. 6-9 into account, it was obvious that stronger lightning test conditions caused severe damages such as larger damaged area and deeper damaged thickness in specimens. On the contrary, both positive and negative charging voltage did not show characteristic damage behavior. Hence, in the test, polarity of charging voltage does not seem to have significant effects on damage of specimens caused by lightning strike.

Fig. 5 Typical Damaged length and area

a) Condition I b) Condition II
c) Condition III d) Condition IV
Fig. 6 Visual appearances of tested specimen A

a) Condition I b) Condition II
c) Condition III d) Condition IV
Fig. 9 Internal damage of testes Specimen A

a) Condition I b) Condition II
c) Condition III d) Condition IV
Fig. 7 UT of tested specimen A

a) Visual appearance b) Result of UT
Fig. 8 Overview and UT of specimen A, condition IV

3-2. Effects of carbon fiber used in skin panels

In this report, specimens that had skin panels made of different kinds of carbon fiber were exposed to lightning tests. In order to compare the effects of these carbon fibers to lightning strikes, specimen B (K63712, 1mm thickness skin panel) and specimen C (TR 50S, 1mm thickness skin panel) in Table 1 were also tested under condition I to IV in Table 2. Visual appearances and UT results of tested specimens were shown in Fig. 10 (specimen B) and Fig. 11 (specimen C). Regardless of kinds of skin panels, the stronger testing conditions were, the larger and deeper damage in specimens were observed. However, by comparing at the same test condition, specimen C showed larger damaged area. In addition, cross sectional observation was also seen in Fig. 12 (specimen B) and Fig. 13 (specimen C). Although these specimens did not show any damage in the core layers, larger delaminations were observed in specimen C (Fig. 13).

Previously, relationships between peak current, electrical charge of tested lightning strikes and damage behavior of tested specimens were reported [4]. These relationships were also investigated in this paper. The relationship between peak current of lightning strike and damaged depth was shown in Fig. 14 and the relationship between electrical charge and damaged area was depicted in Fig. 15. While no significant numeric difference was observed in Fig. 14 among specimen A, B and C, damaged area was different among these specimens in Fig. 15. Since tested specimen A, B and C did not show breakage in the core layers, no significant difference should be observed. However, as shown in visual appearance

observations and UT results (Fig. 6, 7, 10 and 11), damaged area was numerically different among specimen A, B and C. Specimen C has the steepest inclination; by contrast, specimen A does the most gradual in Fig. 15. Since skin panel of specimen A was made of K13C2U and the fiber has lower electrical resistivity (Table 1), current from lightning strike could flow faster in specimen A than in specimen C. In addition to the electrical property, K13C2U also has higher thermal conductivity than TR 50S. Because of the property, heat in specimens caused by electrical resistance would disperse faster in specimen A than specimen C. Therefore, smaller damage area was shown on specimen A. Specimen B showed the middle damaged area between specimen A and C, and it may attribute to electrical resistivity and thermal conductivity of K63712, which are between K13C2U and TR 50S. From these observation results of tested specimens, a skin panel equipped with carbon fiber which has lower electrical resistivity and higher thermal conductivity would perform better in regards to damage caused by lightning strikes.

a) Condition I

b) Condition II

c) Condition III

d) Condition IV

Fig. 10 Overview and UT result of specimen B

a) Condition I

b) Condition II

c) Condition III

d) Condition IV
Fig. 11 Overview and UT result of specimen C

a) Condition I b) Condition II
c) Condition III d) Condition IV
Fig. 12 Cross sectional observation of specimen B

a) Condition I b) Condition II
c) Condition III d) Condition IV
Fig. 13 Cross sectional observation of specimen C

Fig. 14 Relationship between peak current and damaged thickness of specimens with 1mm thickness skin panels

Fig. 15 Relationship between Electrical charge and damaged area of specimens with 1mm thickness skin panels

3-3. Effects of thickness of skin panels

Effects of thickness of skin panels were also investigated. Under the four testing conditions as shown in Table 2, specimen D and E, both of them had 0.5 mm thickness skin panels, were exposed to lightning tests. Visual appearance, UT and cross sectional observations were conducted and these results under condition IV were shown in Fig. 16 (specimen D) and Fig. 17 (specimen E). Under the stronger test condition IV, specimen D and E showed matrix cracks in their core layers. Relationship between peak current and damaged thickness of tested specimens was described in Fig. 18 and relationship between electrical charge and damaged area was seen in Fig. 19. Since matrix of core layers of specimen D under condition IV and specimen E under condition III and IV were observed, deeper damaged thickness was shown in Fig. 18. While specimen D (K63712, 0.5 mm thickness skin panel) and specimen B (K63712, 0.5 mm thickness skin panel) showed no significant different damage area

caused by lightning strikes, specimen E (TR 50S, 0.5mm thickness skin panel) had larger damaged area than specimen C (TR 50S, 1mm thickness skin panel) did. Specimens equipped with thinner skin panels showed deeper and larger damage than those equipped with thicker skin panels. Particularly, in terms of damaged thickness, specimens under condition IV indicated the clear difference between 0.5 mm thickness skin panels (Fig. 18) and 1 mm thickness ones (Fig. 14).

a) Overview

b) UT

c) Cross sectional observation

Fig. 16 Observation of specimen D under condition IV

a) Overview

b) UT

c) Cross sectional observation

Fig. 17 Observation of specimen E under condition IV

Fig. 18 Relationship between peak current and damaged thickness of specimens with 0.5 mm thickness skin panels

Fig. 19 Relationship between peak current and damaged thickness of specimens with 0.5 mm thickness skin panels

For further investigation of effects of thickness of skin panels, lightning strike tests under condition IV was conducted with specimen F (K13C2U skin panel, 0.6 mm thickness), G, H, I (K13916 skin panel, 1, 0.5, 0.1 mm thickness), and J (K63712 skin panel, 0.2 mm thickness). These tested specimens were inspected with visual appearance observation, UT and cross sectional observation and these results are shown in Fig. 20 - 24. Although tested specimen F had larger area of delamination than that of specimen A (K13C2U skin panel, 1 mm thickness, Fig. 6 and 7), the core layer was intact (Fig. 20c). By comparing tested specimen G, H, and I, damaged area enlarged and thickness deepened in accordance with decrease in skin panel's thickness (Fig. 21, 22 and 23). Tested specimen J showed larger delamination area and deeper matrix cracks in the core layer than specimen B (K63712, 1 mm thickness skin panel, Fig. 10d and 13d) and D (K63712, 0.5 mm thickness skin panel, Fig. 16). From these observation results of tested specimens, thicker skin panels have better ability to protect the core layers from damage caused by lightning strikes.

a) Overview
b) UT
c) Cross sectional observation
Fig. 20 Observation of specimen F (K13C2U, 0.6mm thickness skin), condition IV

a) Overview
b) UT
c) Cross sectional observation
Fig. 21 Observation of specimen G (K13916, 1mm thickness skin), condition IV

a) Overview
b) UT
c) Cross sectional observation
Fig. 22 Observation of specimen H (K13916, 0.5mm thickness skin), condition IV

c) Cross sectional observation
Fig. 23 Observation of specimen I (K13916, 0.1mm thickness skin), condition IV

a) Overview
b) UT
c) Cross sectional observation
Fig. 24 Observation of specimen J (K63712, 0.2mm thickness skin), condition IV

a) Overview
b) UT
c) Cross sectional observation
Fig. 25 Observation of specimen K (K63712, 0.2mm thickness skin), condition IV

Relationship between skin panel thickness and damaged thickness of specimens under test condition

IV is shown in Fig. 25. Items are assorted by kind of carbon fiber that is used in a skin panel of a tested specimen. At 1 mm of skin panel thickness in the graph, all tested specimens did not show matrix cracks in the core layers. Around 0.5 mm thickness, while no thicker damage in specimens that used K13C2U and K13916 as skin panels was observed, matrix cracks were observed in specimens that used TR 50S and K63712 as skin panels. The phenomenon would be related to electrical resistivity of carbon fiber that is used in a skin panel. Because of lower electrical conductivity of K13C2U (Table 1), lightning current would flow fast in-plane direction enough to avoid propel to depth direction, and as a result, K13C2U showed thicker damage than the other specimens. Skin panels that have 0.1 to 0.2 mm thickness would not have sufficient ability to protect the core layers from lightning strikes because both K13916 (specimen I) and K63712(specimen J) showed damaged core layers.

Relationship between skin panel thickness and damaged area is also depicted in Fig. 26. Items are assorted by kind of carbon fiber that is used in a skin panel of a tested specimen. At 1.0 mm thickness of skin panels, generally smaller damaged area is observed than that of specimens that have thinner skin panels. Data in the graph is scattered in Fig. 26 and this phenomenon would be due to delamination caused by rapid expansion of volume of vaporized resin, which is caused by resistive heat produced by flowing lightning current. Rapid expansion would occur randomly; thus, different damaged area was observed on specimens.

Fig. 25 Relationship between skin panel thickness and damaged thickness, test condition IV

Fig. 26 Relationship between skin panel thickness and damaged area, test condition IV

4. Conclusion

Lightning strike tests on specimens that have different kinds of skin panels were conducted with different testing conditions and tested specimens were exposed to observation including overview, UT and cross sectional views.

Four different lightning strike test conditions were applied to specimens A (K13C2U, 1 mm thickness skin panel). From observation of tested specimens, larger damaged area caused by lightning strikes was observed in accordance with stronger testing conditions.

In order to compare effects of kind of carbon fiber used in a skin panel, specimen A, B (K63712, 1mm thickness skin panel) and C (TR 50S, 1mm thickness skin panel) were exposed to lightning strike tests. Among these specimens, specimen A showed the thinnest damaged thickness and smallest damaged area. Since K13C2U has lower electrical resistivity and than the others, lightning current would flow fast in the specimen enough to avoid causing damage in the specimen. In addition, higher thermal conductivity of K13C2U would also prevent enlarging delamination area caused by resistive heat produced by lightning current. Since heat would disperse faster due to the higher thermal conductivity, specimen A could avoid severe damage.

Observation of tested specimens that had thinner skin panels was also conducted. Specimens that have thicker skin panels show smaller damaged area than that of specimens which have thinner skin panels. In order to equip sufficient lightning strike protection, thicker skin panels are preferable.

5. References

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